

Surveying Deliberation Practices and Methodological Needs in Robotics Software Engineering

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Abstract. This paper presents findings from two surveys on challenges and preferences in developing robust deliberation for autonomous robots. The first survey targeted robotics experts and software developers to understand workflows and methodological needs in developing deliberation systems, guiding the development of an open-source toolbox for robust deliberation technology within the EU project CONVINCENCE. The toolbox includes AS2FM, enabling formal modeling of robotic systems for quantitative verification. The second survey, conducted at ROSCon 2024, evaluated AS2FM and other deliberation tools, providing feedback for further development. This work advances user-centric robotics software design and fosters collaboration in autonomous deliberation technologies.

1 Introduction

The rapid advancement of robotics and autonomous systems raises the need for robust and reliable deliberation for long-term autonomy, enabling informed decision-making in dynamic environments. Deliberation technologies, as behavior trees (BTs), finite-state machines (FSMs), and task planning, are essential for autonomy but present challenges in integration, usability, and verifiability, esp. for robot-environment interaction and internal system communication.

Ensuring robust autonomy in novel or rare situations remains a key research goal. Most efforts focus on testing individual software components for safety and reliability [8], often neglecting environment and system-wide interactions as in Robot Operating System (ROS) applications [15]. While current deliberation techniques combine preprogrammed behaviors, logical inference, and learning-based approaches [9], they lack formal verification, making it hard to guarantee correct behavior [8], e.g., in terms of temporal logic properties. Existing approaches validate components in isolation, rely on resource-intensive system-wide testing, or use extensive software-hardware models [5]. This highlights the need for tools ensuring robustness through formal modeling with verification and validation (V&V) [4,3,14]. Projects like Papyrus for Robotics [16] and SmartSoft [17] haven been extended to support verification in CARVE [3], SCOPE [2], and

SafeCC4Robotics [12]. However, no existing tool combines deliberation, learning, perception, and control while offering modelling languages and verification tools. This gap hinders the adoption of advanced cognitive capabilities in industry. Ensuring robustness requires verifying entire robotic systems within their environment, as classic testing alone cannot provide guarantees of correct long-term operation and efficient anomaly handling at design time.

To address these challenges, the CONVINCENCE EU Horizon project developed an open-source toolbox [10,18] for application-specific deliberation systems, enabling robust long-term operation in dynamic environments. A survey among robotics experts and developers captured insights into workflows, preferences, and needs in autonomous deliberation. Based on these findings, AS2FM [7] (Autonomous Systems to Formal Models) was developed to translate ROS 2 system components (e.g., BTs, skills, and communication features) into a formal model (in terms of a Markov Decision Process (MDP)) of the entire robotic system for statistical model checking of temporal logic properties with Storm [11]. A follow-up survey at the ROSCon 2024 workshop *Hands-on with ROS 2 Deliberation Technologies* assessed AS2FM and other deliberation tools through real-world applications, identifying strengths, limitations, and ideas for future improvements of the deliberation technologies of CONVINCENCE.

This paper synthesizes insights from both surveys, offering an overview of deliberation practices and methodological needs in robotics software engineering. By addressing developers’ preferences and challenges, we aim to increase tools’ capabilities and foster collaboration in the robotics community. Section 2 presents findings from the initial survey, Section 3 details AS2FM’s evaluation at ROSCon 2024, and Section 4 discusses future tool development needs.

2 CONVINCENCE Autonomous Systems Developer Survey

To support the development of robust deliberation capabilities in autonomous robots, a quantitative survey was conducted between January and April 2024. It gathered insights from robotics experts and developers on deliberation practices, models, and the use of formal verification. Participants were acquired online via public calls for participation on LinkedIn, ROS discourse, mailing lists, at robotics and verification conferences, etc. The survey received 91 responses, with 60 fully completed. Respondents were introduced to key terminology: *Deliberation logic* describes the specific instance of logic executed by the system (e.g., point-to-point navigation). *Deliberation language* refers to the language used to define a deliberation logic (e.g., BTs, FSMs, Markov Chains). *Deliberation engine* is the software or library running a deliberation language (e.g., SMACC, BehaviorTree.CPP, FlexBE [19]). An interactive page with plots illustrating the results is available online with a summary in a flyer. The full dataset is accessible on Zenodo [1]. The findings highlight current trends and areas for improvement, guiding the development of the CONVINCENCE open-source software toolbox.

Participants’ Background. The survey was completed by software developers (60%), application and system engineers (25%), researchers (6.67%) or managers

(8.33%). They work in SMEs (43.33%), academia (36.67%), and large corporations (10%). Most respondents focus on mobile ground robot navigation (41.67%) or mobile manipulation (28.33%), others are working on stationary industrial manipulation (8.33%), aerial (8.33%), and underwater robots (6.67%). Their robots mainly operate in outdoor unstructured environments (30%), industrial settings (25%), or warehouses (16.67%); dynamic, uncertain environments where the CONVINCe toolbox aims to enhance deliberation robustness. A majority (76.66%) identifies as experts or proficient in autonomous system deliberation, ensuring the study’s representativeness. Most use deliberation for task planning (84.75%) and implementing system skills (61.02%), others apply it to fallback logic, navigation, behavior selection, and configuring robot architecture. This confirms that CONVINCe’s focus on robust deliberation through task and motion planning, and system-wide modeling (ROS communication, BTs, BT plugins, skills, environment of robot) in AS2FM aligns with user needs.

Deliberation Languages.

Fig. 1 (left) shows that BTs (77.97%), FSMs (64.41%), and hand-coded if-else structures (54.24%) are the most regularly used deliberation languages, highlighting the tendency to use well-designed,

accessible deliberation languages. However, the high percentage implementing logics by hand suggests that existing tools do not provide specific deliberation strategies, that developers end up implementing themselves. When evaluating preferences of deliberation languages (Fig. 1, right), a significant shift was observed wherein over 52.5% of respondents prefer BTs, compared to 18.64% who prefer FSM. Moreover, on a scale 0-10 ((not) interested using BTs), 71.66% rated them between 7 and 10. This highlights not only a strong preference for BTs as a deliberation language but also reinforces CONVINCe’s decision to center its tooling around it. Cross-analysis (Fig. 2, right) reveals BTs are favored because they are easy to understand (83.8%, (strongly) agree), modify (83.9%), and implement (74.2%), though debugging (64.6%) and comparison with other implementations (42%) remain challenging. These deficiencies could be improved with verification. Those not currently using BTs are still open to trying them, with the majority rating their willingness above 5 (0-10 scale). Free-text answers highlight key requirements for practical deliberation languages: clear visualization of functional logic, direct language integration in APIs of interfacing tools, easy real-world deployment, clear documentation, formal guarantees, scalability, extendability, composability, debugging, and modifiability. With the open source toolbox of CONVINCe including comprehensive documentation and tutorials, we try to satisfy these needs.

Debugging & Testing. For debugging deliberation logic, 61.02% use ROS diagnostic tools (e.g., rostopic, rqt_console), followed by language specific debugging

Fig. 1. Used (left) and preferred (right, same color scheme) deliberation languages in % of answers.

tools for Python (52.54%) and C++ (49.15%). Logging BT traces (45.76%) and using Groot from BehaviorTree.cpp (37.29%) are also common. Testing of the deliberation logic is primarily done in simulation (88.14%) or manually on the actual system (77.97%), with fewer using unit tests (44.07%) or model checking (15.25%). These results highlight a gap in generic debugging, and verification tools, especially since none of the tools referenced to be used by the participants provide formal correctness guarantees. However, it also shows that model checking is not completely unknown to this community. To handle unforeseen events, 68.97% rely on generic fallbacks, while 25.86% implement blocking reactions. However, these methods do not ensure robust long-term autonomy in unknown environments, reinforcing the need for formal verification and situation learning with feedback loops to planning and navigation, that is the goal of CONVINCENCE.

Participants were asked to rate their satisfaction with currently used testing methods (Fig. 2, left). Both simulation and manual testing were rated highly (≥ 4 on a 1-5 scale) by 69.49% and 61.4% of participants respectively. Model checking was lesser-known (34.55% were unable to rate it), yet 21.82% of those familiar with it expressed high satisfaction. This suggests that while model checking is underutilized due to lack of tools, it is worth supporting the need to make it more accessible. Only 33.33% were satisfied with available testing methods for their preferred deliberation logic, leaving room for strengthening methods currently underexplored in robotics, like model checking. This is underpinned by 77.58% expressing a need for more systematic testing and verification of deliberation engines. Free-text responses emphasized that developers want to ‘make [their] system more robust’ and handle the complexity of robot systems. They also mentioned ‘The big missing part is to [make] the context of the decision making [process] more explicit[. . .] So, any progress in making verification more systematic is a gain’. This further supports CONVINCENCE’s goal of enhancing verification for robust, long-term robot autonomy.

Fig. 2. Satisfaction with testing methods for deliberation logics and rating of BTs.

Formal Models. The introduction of model checking is hindered by the lack of formal representations of deliberation logics. 81.03% of developers do not use formal models (e.g., Markovian Processes, Channel Systems) to develop them. Even among those who claimed to have a formal model, many responses could not be classified as such, suggesting the actual percentage is even higher. Despite this,

43.86% of developers are willing to invest effort in writing a formal model if it enables systematic testing and verification. 36.84% were undecided, highlighting the need to raise awareness of formal methods in robotics. Cross-analysis shows that 52% of those seeing the need for systematic verification would invest time, though some recognize high effort without better tooling. Participants reluctant to adopt formal models cited high effort, code changes, and expert knowledge as barriers, yet many are open to explore them. Most respondents (36.36%) would dedicate 10-20% of their total development time to systematic verification, with 67.27% willing to invest up to 30%, highlighting the desire for tools targeting effective and accessible formal verification. Asked for their preferred format or language in writing a formal model, developers favored a BT-compatible approach, ideally close to BT.cpp XML and a language like Python. These insights inspired the development of AS2FM, allowing to model a system based on ROS 2 communication and BT.cpp, including the robot’s environment. In general, the findings suggest there is demand amongst the robotics community for robust, verifiable robotic systems. The CONVINCE toolbox addresses this problem by formally modelling the complete robotic architecture in AS2FM using familiar formalisms (BTs, MDPs), lowering the entry barrier for developers.

3 ROSCon 2024 ROS 2 Deliberation Technologies Survey

At ROSCon 2024, the *ROS Deliberation Community Group* hosted a *Hands-on with ROS 2 Deliberation Technologies* workshop showcasing the diversity of deliberation technologies, including BTs, FSMs, task planning, and verification and validation systems. Participants tackled predefined tasks using BehaviorTree.CPP, FlexBE [19], `ros_bt_py`, SkiROS2 [13], and AS2FM [7], guided by the tools’ maintainers. A survey [6] conducted at the end gathered feedback on these tools, identifying strengths and limitations in different areas. The full results are available online [6]. In the following, we mostly focus on results concerning AS2FM. The survey received 86 responses with 65 fully completed.

Participants’ Background. Respondents’ demographics align with the first study: 43% work in small & mid-sized enterprises, 26.7% in large corporations, and 23.3% in research institutes, the rest is self-employed or in other associations. Experience in AI and robotics is high, with 66.2% having worked there for at least three years. However, experience with robotic deliberation is lower, with 53.9% being beginners, 33.7% proficient, and only 7% experts. Familiarity with tools for implementing deliberation is very limited (around 5% or lower), except for BT.cpp (26.7%), while newer tools (AS2FM, SkiROS2) are largely unfamiliar.

Tool Comparisons. A meta-observation from the survey is that 20-40% of participants often marked N/A when rating tools, i.e., did not feel confident in answering the question, indicating a need for greater exposure to recent deliberation technologies. Overall, setup procedures were rated well across tools (scale 1-5, 5 = very easy), with many participants voting ≥ 4 : BT.cpp (64.7%), FlexBE (58.8%), AS2FM (45.9%), SkiROS2 (40%), and `ros_bt_py` (38.8%). Notably, AS2FM received the most 5 point ratings (36.47%), directly followed by BT.cpp

(35.3%) (all others only 15-20%), reporting a positive installation process despite the tool’s complexity. There were no technical issues with AS2M. For the other tools they could be fixed by the workshop instructors. Execution speed and responsiveness were generally well received, with satisfaction levels highest for BT.cpp (73%), followed by AS2FM (59.2%), FlexBE (50%), ros_bt_py (28.8%), and SkiROS2 (27%) (≥ 4 on scale 1-5, very unsatisfied to very satisfied).

Feedback on AS2FM underscored its uniqueness and potential: participants valued its ability to ‘provide reliability insights otherwise unavailable’, noted that ‘no other tool like this exists’, and that ‘it [covers] far more scenarios/edge-cases than one could realistically write otherwise’. However, they recognized the challenge of requiring a formal system model, which adds effort and poses risks of discrepancies between the model and reality. Some found the syntax challenging, while others considered it ‘simple to use’, highlighting a need for tailored onboarding resources. To address these concerns, we provide online documentation and tutorials, will focus on improving model traceability, and increase interpretability of the results by visual inspection tools.

As expected, AS2FM was rated the hardest tool to learn, similar to SkiROS2, reflecting the complexity of both tools, indicating that more awareness and training of developers for formal verification is needed. All of that has to be interpreted in the light that many participants were beginners in robotic deliberation. Many respondents (41.5%) were uncertain about recommending AS2FM for future projects, more than for other tools. However 24.6% indicated they would consider it after improvements were implemented, the highest proportion among all tools. Given its early development stage and the participants’ limited prior exposure to formal verification, this cautious optimism reinforces the need for more training and awareness within the community.

4 Conclusion

The surveys provide valuable insights into deliberation in robotics and its challenges. BTs are the most widely used deliberation language, while the reliance of developers on manual validation and simulation, reveals a gap in systematic verification tools. Formal models are underutilized despite their recognized value, emphasizing the need for accessible, well-supported verification tooling centered around BTs. Newer tools like AS2FM show strong potential but require better onboarding and usability. While participants appreciate its unique verification capabilities, they highlight challenges in modeling effort, syntax complexity, and interpretability of the results. Future work will focus on these points to increase the awareness of formal methods to bridge the gap between research advancements and benefits in robotics engineering. By addressing these challenges, CONVINCENCE aims to make systematic verification more accessible, ultimately enhancing the reliability of autonomous systems.

Acknowledgements. The work was supported by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Program, Grant 101070227 (CONVINCE).

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